

A Dynamic Concept of Computing Points on 1D Length

In physics, length is a fundamental and essential concept that plays a central role in describing the physical world. It is a scalar quantity, meaning it is fully described by a single real number and does not have a direction associated with it. The measurement of length is crucial for understanding the dimensions, sizes, and distances of objects, as well as for quantifying various physical phenomena. The standard unit of length in the International System of Units (SI) is the meter (m). The meter was originally defined in terms of the Earth's circumference, but it is now defined based on the speed of light. One meter is approximately equal to the distance that light travels in a vacuum in $1/299,792,458$ seconds. This definition ensures a constant and precise measure for length across different conditions. In addition to the meter, other units of length are used in specific contexts. For example, the nanometer (nm) is often employed in discussions related to atomic and molecular scales, while larger units like the kilometer (km) are suitable for expressing longer distances. The accurate measurement of length is achieved using various instruments, depending on the scale of the objects being measured. For small lengths, tools such as rulers, calipers, and micrometers are common. In contrast, larger lengths may be measured using devices like tape measures, odometers, or surveying equipment. The concept of length extends beyond the one-dimensional measurement of straight-line distances. In physics, the path length traveled by an object is a critical factor, especially in the study of motion. Concepts such as displacement and distance involve the consideration of length in different ways. Displacement refers to the change in position of an object, often measured in a straight line between two points, while distance is the actual path traveled, which may involve changes in direction. Length is a key parameter in many fundamental equations of physics. For instance, in kinematics, the relationship between speed, time, and distance is expressed through the equation ($s = vt$), where (s) is the distance traveled, (v) is the speed, and (t) is the time. Similarly, in mechanics, the concept of leverage and torque relies on the measurement of lengths in determining mechanical advantage. In conclusion, length in physics is a foundational concept that permeates various branches of the discipline. Its precise measurement and understanding are crucial for accurately describing the physical world, from the microscopic realm of particles to the vast distances between celestial bodies. The definition and measurement of length have evolved over time, and the concept continues to be a cornerstone in advancing our comprehension of the universe.

Before delving into the main topic, let us discuss the 0-dimensional point and Planck's length.

In the realm of physics, a point is a representation of infinitesimal spatial extent, or more precisely, the absence of it. A 0-dimensional point is a theoretical entity, a position in space devoid of any dimensions—no length, no width, and no height. It stands as the elemental building block upon which the tapestry of the physical world is woven. At the heart of this exploration lies the fusion of physics and mathematics. In physics, points play a pivotal role in understanding the nature of particles and their interactions. Quantum mechanics, a cornerstone of modern physics, relies on the concept of points to describe the fundamental constituents of matter. Subatomic particles, such as electrons, are often treated as points with no spatial extension, existing at precise locations in the quantum realm. Within the framework of physics, the 0-dimensional point becomes a beacon in the mathematical landscape. In classical mechanics, a point particle is a theoretical object with mass but zero size, simplifying complex physical systems into manageable mathematical models. These point particles follow trajectories dictated by Newtonian laws, enabling physicists to make predictions about the motion of objects in space. Venturing into the realm of relativity, the concept of a point takes on new dimensions—both literally and figuratively. In Einstein's general theory of relativity, space-time is a four-dimensional continuum where points are events characterized by their coordinates in space and time. Gravity, according to this theory, is not a force but a curvature in the fabric of space-time caused by the presence of mass. In this intricate dance of geometry and physics, points become integral to the very structure of the universe. Furthermore, the notion of a 0-dimensional point finds resonance in the exploration of subatomic scales. The uncertainty principle, a cornerstone of quantum mechanics, posits that the more precisely we know a particle's position, the less precisely we can know its momentum, and vice versa. This inherent fuzziness at the quantum level challenges our classical intuition about precisely defined points in space. As physicists delve deeper into the mysteries of the cosmos, the concept of a point serves as both a tool and a philosophical pondering. In string theory, a theoretical framework seeking to unify quantum mechanics and general relativity, points are replaced by one-dimensional strings vibrating at different frequencies. This departure from classical notions reflects the evolving nature of our understanding of the fundamental building blocks of the universe. In conclusion, within the tapestry of physics, a 0-dimensional point emerges as a fundamental concept, intertwining with mathematical abstraction to unravel the mysteries of the cosmos. From classical mechanics to quantum realms and the curvature of space-time, the point persists as a guiding beacon in our quest to comprehend the nature of the physical universe.

Planck's length, denoted as " l_p ," stands as a fundamental constant within the realm of theoretical physics. First introduced by the distinguished German physicist Max Planck in 1899, this minute length holds a profound significance in the intricate tapestry of quantum mechanics and the pursuit of understanding quantum gravity. At its core, Planck's length represents the smallest conceivable length scale in the vast expanse of the universe. It marks a boundary below which our conventional understanding of space and distance loses its relevance. This microscopic dimension becomes a critical parameter in the domain where quantum effects reign supreme, challenging the established classical laws of physics. Quantifying the minuteness of Planck's length is a task that underscores its exceptional nature. Measuring approximately 1.616×10^{-35} meters, this scale emerges from the interplay of fundamental constants that govern the fabric of our physical reality. The speed of light (c), Planck's constant (h), and the gravitational constant (G) converge in an intricate dance, encapsulated in the formula for Planck's length:

$$l_p = \sqrt{\{hG / (2\pi c^3)\}} \quad (1)$$

Here, within the confines of this diminutive length scale, the classical edifices of physics, including the venerable general relativity, lose their dominion. It is at the Planck scale that the quantum realm takes precedence, ushering in a realm where our conventional intuitions about space and time undergo a profound transformation. Crucially, Planck's length assumes a central role in the ambitious pursuit of a theory of quantum gravity. This theoretical framework seeks to harmonize the tenets of general relativity with the enigmatic principles of quantum mechanics. By probing the behavior of the universe at these infinitesimal scales, physicists aim to unravel the mysteries encapsulated within the Planck scale. However, the experimental verification of Planck's length remains a formidable challenge. Its astonishingly minute magnitude presents obstacles that stretch the limits of our technological capabilities. Yet, despite these challenges, the pursuit of understanding the universe at the quantum level persists, with Planck's length standing as a guiding beacon in this intricate and profound exploration.

However, the conditions for the existence of the smallest length are as follows:

1. All smallest lengths will be the same.
2. The smallest length of the universe is not only mathematical but also meaningful according to physics; it must be relevant to physics.
3. Any amount of length can be made up of the smallest length of the universe and can be expressed as $(L = n \times S_m)$, where (L) is any amount of length, (n) is a positive whole number ($n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$), and (S_m) is the smallest length.

Keep in mind that if we obtain any fractional value for (n) , considering (S_m) as the smallest length of the universe won't be relevant. For example, if the smallest length of our universe is 7 m and you measure a length of 20 m, the value of (n) is 2.8571428571, which is a fraction. In this scenario, considering the first and second sticks as the smallest length of the universe is not relevant because the third stick is smaller. This illustrates the main concept of quantization.

If we take the Planck's length as the smallest length of the universe, all lengths should follow $(L = n l_p)$, where (l_p) is the Planck's length and $(n = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$. If (n) is a fraction after dividing with Planck's length, that length has no physical existence in our universe.

Quantization of length doesn't imply a gap between two smallest lengths; rather, it is used as a unit (smallest part) that is connected and has a physical meaning.

The Big Bang model suggests that our universe is expanding, and the minimum expansion of length will be the smallest length. This discussion doesn't involve the rate or time; it focuses on the minimum expansion of length.

Quantization plays a crucial role in understanding the universe and physics. If we want to find out the number of 0-dimensional points in space, we must consider that the points in space are not continuous but quantized, according to physics. While mathematics allows for the

imagination of lengths smaller than the Planck's length, the conditions shared earlier must be considered. The number of points in Planck's lengths is two, and lengths that are multiples of the Planck's length have a corresponding number of points. For example, a length that is 2× the Planck's length has three points, and a length that is 5× the Planck's length has six points.

We notice, the number of point on 1D length follows,

$$\Phi = n + 1 \quad (2)$$

There,

n = The number of Planck's length. (Obviously $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$)

Hence, we can write the equation as,

$$\Phi = n + 1$$

$$\Phi = (L / l_p) + 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\Phi = [L / \sqrt{\{hG / (2\pi c^3)\}}] + 1 \quad (4)$$

Equations offer insights into the distribution of points along a 1D length, where the condition $L / l_p = n$ ($n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) holds significance. This relationship intertwines with fundamental constants such as the speed of light, Planck's constant, and Newton's gravitational constant. Expanding our understanding, we can establish connections with additional equations by integrating these constants or introducing pertinent variables, ensuring the resulting relationships are both meaningful and valid within the context.

What becomes apparent is the potential for inspiration to extend this exploration beyond one-dimensional space. While the prospect of determining points within an area or volume emerges, it's essential to acknowledge the complexity of such endeavors. Unlike the straightforward 1D scenario, delving into 2D and 3D introduces challenges, demanding adherence to physical principles.

Crucially, this pursuit goes beyond a mere enumeration of points within geometric shapes. It necessitates consideration of distinct features, akin to the Planck's length, to ensure the derived area and volume maintain physical significance. This implies that the process isn't merely a matter of constructing cubes or circles and tabulating points; rather, it involves a nuanced comprehension of the underlying physics to construct meaningful spatial representations.

In conclusion, the exploration initiated by the initial equation holds promise for extending our understanding to higher dimensions, but the path to determining points within areas and volumes involves complexities that demand careful consideration of fundamental constants and adherence to the principles of physics.

Lastly, the most interesting aspect of the paper is that the Big Bang suggests our universe is expanding. As we have a valid concept concerning the points of length, let us consider that our universe has a length. The length also follows the condition ($L / l_p = n$, where $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$).

Once upon a time, there was no length in the universe, meaning 0 m. Let's put the value in the equation. We get,

$$\Phi = (L / l_p) + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (0 / l_p) + 1 \\ &= (0 + 1) \\ &= 1 \quad (\text{Showed}) \end{aligned}$$

It is notable that the length was 0 m. There was no length, but there was only 1 (0D) point. 0D is the feature of singularity.

We also acknowledge that we have not considered fundamental forces, energy, and other dimensions. However, we have shown that, "0D point is not impossible, even if we use quantization of space-time."

For the first time, we have proved, using Quantum Mechanics (without using relativity), that singularity is possible. However, singularity has many features we currently don't know. We have just proved a feature of singularity, that 0D is possible.

In essence, we hope that this small finding will change our attitude about physics. Even we are capable of measuring points in 1D length. Proving 0D point using quantization is groundbreaking. Furthermore, it can be expected that all equations will be more upgraded, and it will be able to upgrade our technologies. In a word,

Just now, the total civilization and science community have jumped to the next level. It may seem strange according to math and classical physics, but it can be a meaningful way for Quantum Physics. We also thank the audience who has joined with us. Lastly, reminding again,

From now on, you can measure the number of points in our real universe.

Fig.01: The Main Theme of the Paper

Quantization of Length

We notice that,

$$\Phi = n + 1$$

We have not taken the points of the middle of a Planck's length for keeping relevancy with physical effect. Even points are not continuous. Rather points are quantized.

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The End